

(Institute of Natural Products, Canary Islands, Spain) for the ir and pmr spectra of acetyl methyl pomolate (acetyl methyl benthamate). The financial assistance of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

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Triterpenoids from *Dillenia pentagyna*

K. P. TIWARI*, S. D. SRIVASTAVA

and

S. K. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad, U. P.Manuscript received 17 April 1979, revised 20 December 1980,
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DILLENIA pentagyna (Fam: Dilleniaceae) is a medicinal plant^{1,2} and has not been chemically investigated so far. Four triterpenes, lupeol, betulin, betulonic acid and morolic acid have been isolated from the stem bark of this plant and are reported here.

The air-dried powdered stem bark of *D. pentagyna* (2 kg) was extracted with EtOH under reflux for 25 days on a water bath. The extract (2.5 litres) was filtered off, concentrated to 100 ml and poured into H₂O (500 ml). The H₂O insoluble material was extracted with hexane and C₆H₆ respectively. The hexane soluble fraction on column chromatography over alumina gave two compounds called compound-A and compound-B. The C₆H₆ fraction on concentration gave a dirty white solid mass which was again extracted with petrol (60-80°) and CHCl₃ respectively and gave Compound-C and Compound-D.

Compound-A, on crystallization (MeOH : CHCl₃) furnished silky needles, C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺ 426), m.p. 213-14°. It gave LB test for triterpenoids, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm⁻¹ 3325 (OH), 1639, 1380 and 885. It was identified as lupeol by mixed m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with an authentic sample³.

Compound-B, crystallized as white needles from aq. EtOH, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442), m.p. 251-52°. It

gave the usual tests for triterpenoids, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm⁻¹ 3350 (OH). From the detailed study of its ir, ¹H nmr, ms and derivatives it was proved to be betulin⁴ which was further confirmed by co-tlc and co-ir with authentic specimen.

Compound-C was crystallized from EtOH as white needles, C₃₀H₄₆O₃ (M⁺454), m.p. 250-52° (d). It gave LB test and noller reaction for terpenoids, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm⁻¹ 3460, 1640, 1380, 880. It formed a monomethyl ester, m.p. 164-65° (Found; C, 79.50; H, 10.25; C₃₁H₄₈O₃ required; C, 79.48; H, 10.25%). Its ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃, δ , TMS) showed a signal at 3.60(s) for a carbomethoxy group. It formed a semicarbazone, m.p. 282-83° and an oxime, m.p. 236° (d). The identity of this compound with betulonic acid⁴ was established by mixed m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

Compound-D was crystallized from EtOH, C₃₀H₄₈O₃, (M⁺456), m.p. 272-73°. It gave LB test for triterpenoids. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm⁻¹ 3450, 1640, 804, 828. It formed an acetate (Ac₂O/Py, m.p. 255-57°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1740) and a methyl ester (CH₂N₂, m.p. 228-29°; ¹H nmr, CDCl₃, δ , 3.60 ppm, 3H) showing the presence of -OH and -COOH groups in the compound-D. It was identified as morolic acid⁵ by comparison of mixed m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

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The Triterpenoid Constituents of the Leaves of *Nyctanthus arbortristis* Linn

A. S. R. ANJANEYULU, Y. L. N. MURTY,

and

L. RAMACHANDRA ROW

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair

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THE shrub *Nyctanthus arbortristis* Linn¹ (Fam: Oleaceae, Ver. name. Tel: Parijataka) is widely cultivated throughout India as a garden plant. Isolation of nyctanthic acid, a 3-4 secotriterpene